

The Meaning Behind The Meaning: The Analysis Of Texts Related To Prophets Noah, Ibrahim, And Salih Alayhisalam In Isajan Sultan's Story "Unlike The Previous"

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Abstract: This article analyses the texts related to Nuh, Ibrahim, Salih alayhissalam in the story "Unlike the Previous" by the national writer of Uzbekistan, Isajon Sultan.

Keywords — Nuh, Yunus, Ibrahim, Yunus, wind "sarsar", Mountain Tur, Tuvo Valley, Safo Valley, Marva Valley, Maryam, Aziz aka, Surah "Hud".

INTRODUCTION.

Today, the works of Isajon Sultan are the focus of the scientific research community of Uzbek literary studies. A number of studies are being conducted on symbolism, artistic skill, philosophy, and mythological views in the works written by the writer. The artistic synthesis of religious motifs has a special place in the writer's works and is one of the issues researched. Therefore, the study of this issue is of particular importance.

Isajon Sultan talks about how the Dutch scientists modelled Noah's flood in his story "Unlike the Previous", written in the language of the mathematician Aziz, aka the protagonist of the story:

"Last year, Dutch scientists modelled Noah's flood. The result was surprising: all the water on earth wouldn't be enough to cause such a flood. So, the Dutch scientist concluded, "So the flood didn't happen." No, if it was true that there was a flood, then where did all that water come from? Their experiment changed the theory of the earth's crust: it led to the hypothesis that the core of the mother planet contains water, not molten ore.[1.480]

The stories of Noah (a.s.) are mentioned in the Holy Qur'an in 43 verses of 28 suras. [2.26]

He commanded. "Until Our command (the flood disaster) came, and when things became severe, We said, "Oh, Noah!" Take a pair of every animal and your people to it (the ark), except for those who were ordered to drown We mentioned), and allow to board those who believe! "However, those who believe with him are few." (Hud, 40.) [3.226]

If the Dutch had read the following verses of the Holy Qur'an, they would have known and realised that "the hypothesis" (that "there is water in the core of the mother planet, not molten ore") is not a hypothesis only, but the same truth written in the verse of the divine book as early as the 8th century:

"The famous Noah's flood began, and suddenly the sky seemed to be pierced and the earth cracked. It began to rain

from the sky, and water gushed out from the mountain, from the rock, and from the flat land, and the flood began to flow; the whole earth was covered with water, and the waves began to sweep everything into its depth, and all creatures and beings were submerged under water. Only Noah (a.s.) and the people and creatures who were in the ark with him were saved and floated on the surface of the water. [4.27]

It was said: "Then it was said: "O Earth! Drink your water! O sky! Hold on (stop raining)!" The water dried up, the command was obeyed, and the ark landed on Juvdi (the mountain), crying, "Death to the oppressors, the people of Demon!" -. ("Hud", 44.) [5.226]

Before the end of the story, the writer again draws the reader's attention to Noah's flood. Aziz aka, asks the mathematician a question about whether Noah's flood happened or not. "I do not know. "There is nothing about it in the oldest history", he sneers and thinks about false history (the history that was falsified during the former USSR), and, in turn, the following passage is offered, which is also related to patriotism (a sense of being proud of one's ancestors):

"Tell me, did Noah's flood really happen?" "I do not know. There is nothing about it in the earliest histories." "Does it mean that Prophet Noah didn't exist there at all?" Aziz aka said sarcastically. "Do they say that Adam and Eve did not exist, too? Since when did false history reject true history? Did Beruni, Mirzo Ulugbek, Bukhari, Ghazali, and hundreds of other scientists... lie?"[6.480]

The mathematician, making an analogy about the sea of meanings, emphasises that only some of those who dive deep into this sea will have a chance, those who cannot dive deep will come back empty-handed and hopeless, and the sharks of the sea will swallow weak thoughts. If it is called the Sea of Obedience and Submission, he says that those who are disobedient will be bait for fish, implying, as Jonah did:

"You will realise that even the pumpkin with leaves on you is not in vain. If you pass through it and wander through the heat of Arabia, you will see that the desert is as barren as the heart of an unbeliever. You will come across a stone in the desert; if you touch it, it will stand up as a camel of meaning.

You will see a cow there; if you slaughter it and hit the dead man with a piece of it, he will revive and tell you who killed him. If you take four birds and grind them, mix bird carcasses thoroughly, and take them to the mountains on four sides and call them, they will fly again as before." [7.454]

The sentences in the passage "If you take four birds and grind them, mix bird carcasses thoroughly, and take them to the mountains on four sides and call them, they will fly again as before..." are related to the verses of the Holy Qur'an.

Despite the fact that the heart of Ibrahim (a.s.) was full of faith, he wanted to see the power of God with his own eyes and knowledge. One day he prayed to God and said:

"Remember (O Muhammad!), when Ibrahim said: "O Lord, show me how you resurrect the dead", Allah said: "Don't you believe me?" he said. Ibrahim said: "No, but let my soul be more comforted." Allah said: "Take four birds and gather them in front of you (and cut them into pieces and merge them), then place them in pieces on every mountain (around you), then call them, (they will be resurrected) and come to you immediately. Know that Allah has almighty power and wisdom. (Al-Baqara, 260.) [8.44]

The teacher continued his thoughts: "Life sometimes throws a person into the mill and then onto the fire. But God preserves human health. Hey, you good guys! Are some of you not coming out of the fires of life unscathed like Abraham?" [9.455]

God Almighty sent Ibrahim (a.s.) as a prophet to Babylonian polytheists. Instead of thanking God for a very comfortable and luxurious life, the Babylonians practised idolatry. Namrud ibn Kan'an ibn Kosh ruled that tribe. He claimed to be a god. Abraham's father, Ozar, was a pagan; he made idols and sold them in the market. When everyone went to the holiday gathering, Abraham broke all the idols and hung an axe around the neck of the biggest idol. They brought Ibrahim and asked who did that. That situation was mentioned in verse 63 of Surah Anbiyya. Ibrahim carefully:

قَالَ بَلْ فَعَلَهُ كَأَبِيئُهُمْ هَذَا فَاسْأَلُوهُمْ إِنَّ النُّوْكَ يَنْطِقُونَ (٦٣)

"(Ibrahim) said: "No. It was the eldest (statue) of them who did that. So, if you ask him, he will answer. By the way, if he can speak, of course. [10.327]

This case is mentioned in verse 68 of Surah Anbiyya:

The polytheists(led by Nimrud) said, "Burn him! If you can do something, help your gods (by doing it)!" [11.327]

They gathered a large amount of firewood, burned it, and then put Ibrahim in a manjanik (an ancient stone throwing weapon) and threw him into the fire. This is exactly what Isajon Sultan meant in the story. Allah Almighty ordered the fire: "We said, "O fire! Be cool and safe, Ibrahim!" [12.327]. This case is mentioned in verse 69 of Surah Anbiyya.

"With the power and grace of Allah, Ibrahim (a.s.) fell into the middle of the fire, became invisible in the smoke and flames, and after the fire was over, came out safely. This was a prophetic miracle given to Ibrahim (a.s.). According to

historians, the place where Ibrahim (a.s.) was thrown into the fire was in the city of Urfa in Turkey, which is still famous. [13.38-39]

Aziz aka the protagonist of the story "Unlike the Previous," continues his thoughts and says the following:

"Sometimes a tree calls out to you like Moses standing in front of you. You will be surprised that the stone turned into a camel and moved on to the ground. Are you used to it when He places a small animal between two stones?" [14.455-456]

In the passage, "the stone rose up from the earth, turning into a camel," which is related to the name of the prophet Salih. The name of the Prophet Salih was mentioned in the Qur'an in the 9th verse of the 4th chapter; his nationality was Arab. The tribe of Thamud was a people who lived in a place called Hijr between Sham (Syria) and Hijaz (Saudi Arabia). Because they lived in mountainous areas, they carved high mountains, built very tall houses, and built cities there. The people of Salih (a.s.) did not believe in his calls; they demanded a prophetic miracle of him: "O Salih, if you bring out a she-camel from the foot of that mountain, we will believe you." Salih (a.s.) prayed, and a she-camel appeared. Salih (a.s.) said to them: "Here is the camel; it grazes on God's land; it does not touch your land. One day she drinks water from the well; one day you drink. If you do any harm to her, there will be total destruction," he warned. [15.35] The author explained the process of the appearance of the camel in detail. At first the stone rose up as a camel and came out of the cave when the people saw it as a she-camel.

It is blessed as follows in verse 64 of Surah Hud of the Holy Qur'an:

"O my people, this is the miraculous camel of God. So leave her to graze on the earth of God and do not harm her; otherwise, all of you will get punishment soon." [16.327]

"Zi Saduq bint Muhayya, who was the most beautiful and rich woman in the tribe, pledged herself to Misda' ibn Makhraj and promised to become his wife if he slaughtered Saleh's camel. Unaiza was an old unbeliever. She called Qudor ibn Salif and promised to give one of her daughters to Qudor for free if he slaughtered Salih's camel. [17.35] They killed that camel. (Verse 77, Surah "Araf") [18.160] After the promised three days, the tribe of Thamud suffered a sudden disaster, and a terrible event happened. In verses 67–68 of Surah "Hud," it is said that they were killed by a terrible scream, while in verse 78 of Surah "A'raf" [19.160], it is reported that they were buried under the ground due to a terrible earthquake.

Now we will analyse another passage from the story "Unlike the Previous":

"Sometimes I feel like an ant crawling with a drop of water in its mouth to save someone who is burning in the fire," he used to say. "What else can I do with that powerful fire? But I keep going on even though I know I can't put it out." [20.456]

Isajon Sultan now draws our attention to the wisdom of "an ant crawling with a drop of water in its mouth", but the writer does not mention the name of prophet Ibrahim, nor does he

refer the name of the Holy Qur'an to the judgement of an erudite reader.

A cruel padishah named Namrud and his people brought the prophet Ibrahim to be burned in the fire. Infidels threw Ibrahim into the fire. No one took his side. Then people saw an ant walking towards the burning fire with water in its mouth and asked him: "O ant, do you know what you are doing? Do you think you can put out such a strong fire?" Then the ant replied: "I will be asked on the Day of Resurrection why I kept silent while the Messenger of God was being burned and hadn't helped him as much as I could."

The talented and knowledgeable national writer of Uzbekistan, Isajon Sultan, does not mention the names of the prophets or the Holy Qur'an in the story "Unlike the Previous", as in many other works. He leaves it to the judgement of the learned reader, who has a certain level of knowledge potential, to find the wisdom of the meaning hidden behind it. In some places, he gives wisdom by mentioning the names of the prophets, which in turn requires more knowledge from the reader, who claims to understand the meaning deeply.

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